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Published: 30th April, 2025**ANALYZING THE INFLUENCE OF FIRM CHARACTERISTICS ON
ENVIRONMENTAL REPORTING: INSIGHTS FROM LISTED OIL &
GAS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA**¹Temitope Abiodun Oje, ²Yua Henry & ³Yua Paul Mkuma¹Scholar, College of Business and Leadership, Eastern University, St Davids, Pennsylvania²College of Management Sciences, Department of Banking and Finance, FPW³Central Bank of Nigeria**D.O.I: 10.5281/zenodo.15577832****ABSTRACT**

This research examined how firm characteristics influence environmental reporting among twelve oil and gas companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group as of December 31, 2023. Using an ex post facto research design, the study applied random effect regression, the Hausman test for model selection, and diagnostic tests to assess issues such as autocorrelation and multicollinearity. The findings indicate that firm size (SIZE) has a positive and significant impact on environmental reporting, with a coefficient of 0.241767, suggesting that larger firms are more likely to engage in such practices. Profitability (PRO) also exhibits a positive and significant effect, with a coefficient of 0.102495, indicating that financially successful firms are more inclined to disclose environmental information. In contrast, leverage (LEV) has a negative but insignificant effect, with a coefficient of -0.006899, suggesting minimal influence on environmental reporting. Firm age (AGE) shows a positive yet insignificant effect, with a coefficient of 0.000919. The constant term (C) is significant at 0.449921, representing baseline environmental reporting levels. The study concludes that while firm size and profitability are key drivers of environmental reporting, leverage and firm age do not play a significant role. It is recommended that regulatory bodies and industry associations provide ongoing support and resources to oil and gas companies, regardless of their age, to foster continuous improvement in environmental reporting over time.

Key words: Age, Environmental reporting, Profitability, Size, Leverage**INTRODUCTION**

Environmental challenges such as pollution, deforestation, erosion, and climate change pose significant threats to environmental quality, public health, and national safety. These issues not only diminish human well-being and disrupt natural ecosystems but also jeopardize global

sustainability. Industrialization, driven by mass production and the extensive use of heavy machinery, has been identified as a major contributor to environmental degradation. Additionally, rapid population growth has led to increasing demands for infrastructure, including housing, utilities, buildings, and food production. The level of environmental contamination has already reached a critical point (Yua, Kazeem & Temitope, 2024; Srinivas, 2014). A company's success or failure is influenced not only by the products or services it provides but also by the complexity of the environment in which it operates (Adediran & Alade, 2013). Consequently, organizations are now expected to demonstrate awareness of environmental concerns and actively address the impact of their operations on both the environment and society by incorporating environmental accountability and reporting (Uwuigbe & Jimoh, 2012).

In the past, businesses paid minimal attention to the environmental damage caused by their operations. However, we have now entered a new era of sustainability, where the importance of maintaining clean air and water is widely recognized (Yua, Kazeem & Temitope, 2024). Consumers are increasingly willing to pay a premium for products produced through environmentally friendly processes, and investors place significant value on corporate environmental responsibility (Uwuigbe, 2011). This shift has led to the rise of environmental accounting. It has been strongly argued that businesses have a moral obligation not only to report their financial performance but also to disclose their impact on both society and the natural environment, ensuring transparency and accountability to various stakeholders (ACCA, 2012). Environmental reporting involves organizations voluntarily sharing information about their environmental impact with stakeholders. This communication takes various forms, including annual reports, independent environmental reports, brochures, pamphlets, and documentaries (Yua, Akume, Ityavyar, James, 2024; Gray & Bebbington, 2017). Through environmental accounting, auditing, and disclosure, organizations can demonstrate their commitment to addressing stakeholder concerns regarding sustainability.

Improper waste management, particularly the illegal dumping of industrial and construction waste on public lands, has become a growing concern. According to statistics from the Wisconsin Department of Natural Resources in the United States, open burning, black smoke emissions, and industrial effluents are among the most significant environmental violations. Transparency in corporate environmental activities highlights the need for strict monitoring of natural resources and the negative impact of corporations on society. The environmental consequences of business activities—especially in manufacturing, oil and gas, and banking—include pollution such as noise, waste generation, hazardous emissions, spills, and environmental degradation (Soomiyol, Wajir, & Yua, 2024). Parmigiani, Klassen, and Russo (2011) emphasize that environmental reporting involves making environmental-related costs more visible through company accounting systems and financial statements. Adeyemi and Ayanlola (2015) further point out that self-inflicted issues, weak regulations, an unfavorable macroeconomic environment, and widespread corruption pose significant challenges to the disclosure of social and environmental accounting information by firms.

Firm characteristics encompass the attributes that define a company's operations and influence its financial performance and long-term sustainability. Key factors such as firm size, age, leverage, and profitability play a crucial role in explaining environmental disclosure practices. Research by Ezhilarasi and Kailash (2015), as well as Soomiyol, Teryima, Yua, and Temitope (2024), highlights that company size, age, profitability, leverage, industry affiliation, and environmental certification significantly impact corporate environmental disclosure. Many scholars emphasize the importance of understanding how firm characteristics influence disclosure policies and identifying the most impactful factors, as this has significant implications for a company's stakeholders. Small businesses are encouraged to report their

environmental practices in their annual reports to enhance competitiveness and overall performance (Emenike, Akamelu, & Umeoduagu, 2017). Additionally, Aghdam (2015) suggests that firms operating in environmentally sensitive industries are more likely to disclose environmental information compared to those in less sensitive sectors.

The growing emphasis on environmental reporting has become increasingly evident in both developed and developing nations, driven by stakeholder demands for greater transparency regarding corporate social and environmental responsibility. Gray, Bebbington, and Walters (2017) observed that investors and other stakeholders are increasingly calling for enhanced disclosure of environmental information. This is due to concerns about the significant costs and liabilities associated with environmental issues, as well as their impact on investment decisions and stakeholder activities. A challenge arises when companies provide insufficient environmental information, making it difficult for users to make informed investment choices. In other words, when the disclosed information falls short of user expectations, an expectation gap emerges. In Nigeria, the corporate sector lacks a well-structured framework for environmental accounting and reporting, as well as comprehensive data on the environmental effects of raw material usage, energy consumption, and natural resource depletion. This gap hinders companies from effectively engaging in environmental reporting. Furthermore, relying solely on environmental reporting based on annual financial statements may not offer a complete representation of a company's environmental responsibility. Alawiye-Adams, AdewaleAdegoke, and Akomolafe (2017) highlighted that companies may portray themselves as environmentally responsible while their operations continue to have adverse environmental impacts.

The broad objective of this study is to examine the effect of firm characteristics and environmental reporting practices of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: Examine the effect of firm size, profitability, leverage, and age on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Firm Characteristics

The increased visibility of an industry sector can drive disclosure as companies aim to avoid excessive pressure and criticism from social activists (Lu & Abeysekera, 2014). Environmentally sensitive industries, such as manufacturing, mining, and oil and gas, are expected to demonstrate to stakeholders that they acknowledge their environmental impact and are taking steps to mitigate or address it. Firm characteristics are defined differently across various studies, depending on the criteria used. However, most research aligns with the view that firm characteristics are linked to organizational resources and objectives. These characteristics can be analyzed using three main criteria: structural, market-related, and capital-related attributes. Structural firm characteristics encompass factors such as firm size, age, profitability, and ownership. Market-related variables include industry type, environmental uncertainty, and market conditions, while capital-related attributes consist of liquidity and capital intensity. This study specifically focuses on the structural aspects of firm characteristics, including firm size, age, leverage, profitability, board independence, and industry membership.

Age: Company age is recognized as a key characteristic that can impact the level of environmental disclosure. It is suggested that a company's age reflects its perceived stability (Liu & Anbumozhi, 2009) and signifies elements of stakeholder influence, strategic direction, and financial performance (Roberts, 1992). Additionally, as companies grow older, their

reputation and engagement in voluntary initiatives, such as environmental protection and transparency in environmental reporting, tend to become more established and valuable (Roberts, 1992; Choi, 1999). Therefore, a positive correlation between company age and the extent of environmental disclosure is anticipated. Size: Firm size is a key factor in assessing a company's operational strength. According to Kabir and Hartini (2014), it is associated with industry profitability, sunk costs, and market concentration. Larger firms tend to have more hierarchical management structures, specialized departments, centralized decision-making, and bureaucratic processes. They also attract greater public attention, face higher expectations for environmental responsibility, and have a broader range of stakeholders. While small firms often depend on personal connections, larger companies pursue business relationships strategically to drive innovation, expand market reach, and meet financial requirements. Firm size is commonly measured by total assets, rather than earlier indicators. Leverage: Leverage, as a company characteristic, can influence the extent of environmental disclosure in two distinct ways. When a firm's debt levels (leverage) rise, investors demand greater transparency regarding the company's operational and environmental performance. However, there is no clear consensus on how leverage impacts the volume of disclosure. On one hand, highly leveraged companies may expand their corporate disclosures to mitigate agency costs, suggesting a positive correlation between leverage and environmental disclosure. On the other hand, firms with lower leverage might have sufficient financial resources to support environmental disclosures and prioritize activities that do not directly impact financial performance. Additionally, environmental disclosures can increase proprietary costs, potentially complicating and raising the costs of credit negotiations. Moreover, highly leveraged companies may have fewer environmental matters to disclose, leading to a negative association between financial leverage and the extent of environmental reporting.

Profitability: Highly profitable companies are often perceived as more credible by the public, leading to increased societal expectations for accountability. Research suggests that these firms tend to address social and environmental issues more swiftly (Cormier & Magnan, 1999, as cited in Ying, Jian, Lu, & Indra, 2014). Failing to meet these legitimacy expectations can negatively impact a company's performance and long-term viability. As a result, highly profitable businesses are anticipated to voluntarily disclose more social and environmental information compared to less profitable ones. However, previous empirical studies have shown mixed findings regarding the relationship between profitability and the level of environmental disclosure. Profitability has been identified as a factor influencing the extent of disclosure among firms, with higher profits making management more inclined to provide detailed information (Inchausti, 1997; Lang & Lundholm, 1993; Wallace & Naser, 1995; Suwaidan, 1997). Conversely, firms experiencing financial losses are less likely to disclose extensive information to avoid drawing attention to their poor performance. Various metrics can be used to measure profitability, including net income, profit margin, return on assets, and return on equity. In this study, return on assets was selected as the profitability indicator.

1.1.2 Environmental Reporting

Environmental reporting refers to the systematic disclosure of information about an organization's environmental impact, policies, and sustainability efforts. It plays a crucial role in corporate social responsibility (CSR), helping stakeholders assess an organization's commitment to environmental sustainability (Kolk, 2008).

1.1.2.1 Component of Environmental Reporting

- i. Carbon Footprint and Emissions: Reports often detail greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, energy consumption, and steps taken to reduce carbon footprints (CDP, 2020).

- ii. **Waste Management:** Organizations disclose waste generation, recycling efforts, and hazardous waste management (ISO 14001, 2015).
- iii. **Water and Resource Usage:** Many reports include data on water consumption, conservation strategies, and sustainable sourcing of materials (GRI, 2021).
- iv. **Biodiversity and Ecosystem Protection:** Companies may outline efforts to protect biodiversity, such as reforestation and conservation projects (UNEP, 2019).

1.1.2.2 Frameworks and Standards in Environmental Reporting

- i. **Global Reporting Initiative (GRI):** A widely used framework providing standardized guidelines for sustainability reporting (GRI, 2021).
- ii. **Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD):** Focuses on financial risks related to climate change (TCFD, 2017).
- iii. **Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP):** Helps organizations report on carbon emissions and climate action (CDP, 2020).
- iv. **ISO 14001:** A standard for environmental management systems that encourages continual improvement (ISO 14001, 2015).

1.1.2.3 Importance of Environmental Reporting

- i. **Enhances Transparency and Accountability:** Builds trust among investors, customers, and regulators (Kolk, 2008).
- ii. **Regulatory Compliance:** Helps organizations meet environmental regulations, such as the EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) (European Commission, 2022).
- iii. **Risk Management:** Identifies potential environmental risks and mitigates negative impacts (TCFD, 2017).
- iv. **Competitive Advantage:** Companies with strong sustainability reports attract investors and environmentally conscious consumers (GRI, 2021).

1.1.2.4 Challenges in Environmental Reporting

- i. **Data Accuracy and Reliability:** Organizations struggle with collecting accurate and verifiable data (CDP, 2020).
- ii. **Standardization Issues:** Different frameworks lead to inconsistencies in reporting (GRI, 2021).
- iii. **Greenwashing Risks:** Some companies exaggerate their environmental efforts to improve their public image (Kolk, 2008).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Legitimacy theory

Legitimacy theory, introduced by Dowling and Pfeffer (1975), is rooted in the concept of organizational legitimacy. It posits that for organizations to thrive, they must align their operations with societal norms and values. According to Deegan (2002), organizations continuously work to ensure their actions are viewed as legitimate by external stakeholders. In response to growing societal and stakeholder expectations, large corporations increasingly disclose their environmental performance, demonstrating a commitment to sustainability. This trend aligns with legitimacy theory, which suggests that organizations voluntarily share environmental information to align with societal expectations and maintain their legitimacy. Companies use such disclosures to manage their reputation, particularly during legitimacy crises when negative public perception threatens their operations. Moreover, the theory proposes that businesses disclose information to present themselves favorably to stakeholders, thereby fostering trust and supporting informed investment decisions. Ultimately, legitimacy theory highlights the importance of environmental transparency in meeting societal expectations, securing resources, and mitigating external risks.

2.3 Empirical Review

Nkwoji (2021) investigated the relationship between environmental accounting and Profitability of selected quoted oil and gas companies in Nigeria from 2012-2017. The study examined the relationship between environmental expenditure and net profit of Nigerian oil and gas companies. It used explanatory, historical, and correlational design and secondary data from annual reports and Nigerian Stock Exchange accounts. Results showed no significant relationship between environmental expenditure and net profit. The study recommends companies focus on adequate environmental spending and disclosure to increase stakeholder trust and transparency, leading to better financial performance.

Handoyo and Angela (2021) examined the relationship between a firm's characteristics and environmental disclosure quality. Firm's characteristics used in the study were size, ownership concentration, age, and leverage. Content analysis of sustainability reporting was applied in this study. The study involved 33 listed firms in Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) that were consistently issued sustainability reporting during 2014-2016. Simultaneous test indicated that characteristics of the firm significantly explained the variance of environmental disclosure quality, also partial test showed that leverage was the only variable significantly influenced by environmental disclosure quality. Salawu, Mamman, Dahiru, Garba and Yunusa (2021) examined the relationship of specific oil and gas firms attributes; firms age, board composition, financial performance, existence of foreign directors on the board and financial leverage with Environmental Disclosures (ED). Data were collected from the published annual reports of nine listed oil and gas firms quoted on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) as at 2018, for a period of seven years (2012-2018). Generalized Least Square (GLS) was used to test the hypotheses. The study established a positive and significant relationship between board composition, financial leverage, existence of foreign directors on the board and environmental disclosure (ED). Also, firm age and financial performance was found not to have significant relationship with environmental disclosure (ED).

Uniamikogbo and Ifeanyichukwu (2021) investigated the relationship between environmental accounting disclosure and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Precisely, the study examined the effect of environmental accounting disclosures on Share Price, Return on Asset and Return of equity of selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The ex-post-facto research design was engaged in this study, using a sample of 40 manufacturing firms. The

secondary source of data collection method was employed using the convenience sampling technique. Data were harvested from the content analysis disclosure index and corporate annual reports of the sampled manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for the period 2010-2019 financial years. The descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and regression analysis were the statistical tools used in the study. Data were analysed with the aid of the panel data regression technique. The findings revealed that environmental accounting disclosures had a significant effect each on Share Price, Return on Asset and Return on equity of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Agyemang et al. (2020) examined the impact of board characteristic on environmental disclosure using data of 34 listed mining companies in China from 2000 to 2018. Multiple regression analysis result showed that both board independence and board size have a significant positive influence on the disclosure of environmental accounting information. While both foreign nationals and females on board have an insignificant relationship with the disclosure of environmental accounting information.

Chariri, Nasir, Januarti and Daljono (2019) examined the effect of institutional ownership, audit committee, and types of industry on environmental investment in Indonesia. The sample consist of 145 companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchanges in the year 2009 - 2015. Findings revealed that environmental investment was significantly affected by types of industry but institutional ownership and audit committee did not influence environmental investment. The review has a period gap because the year is 2019 and they reviewed and stopped at 2015 of which a lot of changes and impact of firm characteristics on environmental reporting might have taken place also the audit committee helps the board directors in overseeing the company's reporting policy and oversees the quality of financial reporting in the company.

Emmanuel, Elvis & Abiola (2019) studied environmental accounting disclosure and performance of listed Companies in Nigeria from 2007 – 2016. Data were analyzed through the use of multiple regression. The result of the study shows that non-financial indicators of environmental disclosure have a positive significant effect on performance, while performance indicator of environmental accounting disclosure has no effect on performance of firms. The gap identified are period gap which studied to 2016 leaving out 2017 and 2018 and a lot of changes might have occurred within that period and performance indicator is important because the success or failure of a company may be determined not only by the products or services it deals with but also by the complexity of its performance in the environment.

Polycarp (2019) conducted a research on environmental accounting and financial performance of oil and gas companies in Nigeria from 2016-2017. Data was collected from annual reports, performance was measured using Return on equity, earnings per share and net profit margin. Multiple regression was used to analyze the data, the study found out that environmental disclosure has no relationship with financial performance. The gap identified is that companies with high profitability ratios may disclose more information in order to prevent negative attention which stems from excess profitability to increase their credibility among investors.

Nwambeke, Udama and Oko (2019) investigated the impact of environment accounting disclosure on financial performance in cement companies in Nigeria from 2006 to 2017. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain the impact of employee safety costs, charitable contribution costs and community development costs on the financial performance of cement companies in Nigeria. The study adopted Ex-Post Facto research design while data obtained from individual annual reports of cement companies were analyzed using panel data regression model. The study found that employee safety costs has negative and significant impact on the financial performance of cement companies in Nigeria; the level of charitable contribution costs has positive and significant impact on the financial performance of cement companies in Nigeria while the level of community development costs has positive and significant impact on

the financial performance of cement companies in Nigeria. The implication of the finding is that companies with better environmental accounting disclosures have higher level of financial performance. The study concluded that environmental accounting disclosure contributes significantly to the profitability of cement companies in Nigeria

Oti & Ogar (2018) examined the impact of environmental and social disclosure on financial performance of selected oil and gas companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange over a period of five years from 2012-2016. Data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of five sampled oil and gas companies. Ordinary least square regression was used to analyze the data. The study revealed that environmental and social disclosure positively affects financial performance. The gap there is only five oil & gas companies were selected which will not be sufficient for the researcher to conclude on the report.

Nwaiwu & Oluka (2018) empirically examined the effect of environmental disclosure on financial performance of firms in Nigeria for a period of five years from 2011-2015. Data were analyzed using multiple regression. The result indicated environmental disclosure has a significant positive effect on financial performance of firms. There is a period gap of two years and this have made the result not sufficient enough because financial performance of a firm will also change with relation to environmental disclosure.

Yahaya (2018) examined the environmental disclosure and financial performance of Listed Environmentally –Sensitive Firms in Nigeria from the period of 2000 to 2016. Data were collected for fifty listed environmentally-sensitive firms. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and multiple regression. The result indicated that environmental disclosure and financial performance have positive and significant relationship. The regression results show that environmental disclosure has positive and significant effect on financial performance. The period under review has a gap of one year which will significantly change the financial performance and also it focuses on one aspect of financial performance which is profitability.

Ezeagba, Racheal, & Chiamaka (2017) conducted a study that investigated the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance companies in Nigeria for a period of ten years from 2006- 2015. Data were analyzed using multiple regression. The study found a significant relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance of companies. There is a period gap of two years and this have made the result not sufficient enough because financial performance of a firm will also change with relation to environmental disclosure. Alawiye-Adams and Akomolafe (2017) examined the inadequacies of corporate environmental disclosures both in quantity and quality amongst manufacturing firms in Nigeria. In order to achieve an in-depth study and wider coverage of the subject-matter; secondary data were obtained from the annual reports of fourteen (14) manufacturing firms. The annual reports were examined for a period of six years (2010 to 2015). The companies were selected based on judgment or purposive sampling. Interpretative content analysis was used to elicit information from the annual reports. The study revealed that corporate environmental disclosure is still at its lowest ebb amongst manufacturing firms in Nigeria and there will be a need for sensitization, regulatory compulsion or government intervention for companies to participate in corporate environmental disclosure. The obvious benefit of this will include the opportunity to resolve issues concerning climate change; particularly dimensions of global warming.

Utile Tarbo and Ikya (2017) examined corporate environmental reporting and the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria using time series data from 2011 to 2015. The study aimed at determining the effect of erosion control reporting, waste management reporting and air pollution reporting on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms

in Nigeria. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design. The sample of the study was drawn from ten manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Regression analysis was employed as the major technique for data analyses. It was found that both erosion control reporting and air pollution reporting has significant effect respectively with firm financial performance while waste management reporting has negative but significant effect on firm financial performance of companies under investigation. The major conclusion reached by this study is that environmental reporting has significant effect on firm financial performance

Ahmed, Zakaree&Kolawole (2016) examine the impact of social and environmental disclosure on financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria for the period of 2001 - 2012. Ten companies were selected; multiple regression was used to analyze the data. The result of the study indicated that environmental disclosure has significant positive impact on earnings per share, and hence profitability of companies. There is a period gap of three years and this have made the result not sufficient enough because the impact on earnings per share and profitability of companies will also change with relation to environmental disclosure.

Majeed, Aziz and Sale (2015) investigate the factors affecting the level of disclosure of information about environmental and social responsibility of listed firms in Pakistan. The study was conducted with a sample of 49 firms with annual reports from 2007 to 2011. The study found that there is a positive and significant impact of the size of the board. The level of board independence, the degree of decentralization and the size of the business have a noticeable impact on the level of disclosure corporate social and environmental responsibility. The results also show the reverse relationship between the representatives by genders and the disclosure level of environmental information. There is period gap of 3 years and also it recognizes on size of the business and board without taking into consideration size of the firm, profitability, leverage and the age of the business to determine its impact on the level of environmental disclosure. Ebiringa (2013) observed, there is considerable consensus in the literature with regards to the effect of firm size on corporate environmental disclosure practices. The effect has been identified as positive as a firm size is expected to increase its information reporting level. There are at least three reasons for this link. First of all, large firms are more willing to disclose information to reduce their political costs, since their higher visibility can easily lead to more litigation and governmental intervention. Secondly, owing to more developed internal reporting system, the costs associated with a higher disclosure level are lower for large firms. Thirdly, smaller firms are more likely to hide crucial information because of their competitive disadvantage within their industry. The authors further posited that firm size would be related to social responsibility activities because larger companies are more likely to be scrutinized by both general public and socially sensitive special interest groups

Galani (2011) conducted a study on the Relationship between Firm Size and Environmental Disclosures. The study investigated the level of environmental reporting in corporate annual reports. Specifically, it investigated the extent to which Greek companies have implemented a set of environmental accounting practices and analyzed the relationship between various firm characteristics and environmental disclosures. The results obtained showed that the degree of development of environmental accounting practices is low and there is a positive relationship between firm size and the disclosure of environmental information in annual reports. However, neither profitability nor listing status seemed to explain differences in environmental disclosure.

3.

METHODOLOGY**3.1 Research Design**

This research adopts an ex-post facto research design. It adopts the use of secondary data (financial statements) and is regarded as being reliable because the financial statements are already audited.

The population of the study comprises of twelve (12) oil and gas companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st December 2023.

3.2 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The twelve (12) listed oil and gas companies financial reports for the relevant years formed the sample size. We are using the entire population so the error margin of representation is near zero. The total population of oil and gas companies that have their financial statements available either on their website or in the office of Nigerian Stock Exchange till 31st December, 2023 is adopted as our sample population.

3.3 Method of Data Analysis

The study employed descriptive statistics of mean, median and standard deviation to study the salient feature of the data used for the study. The study used panel data methodology that made a choice between fixed and random effect regression to test the relationship between the variables of the study. Hausman test for randomization of panel result was used to established the most suitable between fixed effect and random effect regression given our research data so as to minimize the chances error conclusion. Other diagnostic test to enhance the robustness of the result of the study include: JarqueBera test to test for normality of distribution of data, Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier serial correlation test to check for autocorrelation, Breusch Pagan Likelihood ratio test to test for heteroskedasticity in the linear regression model, variance inflation factor (VIF) to test for multicollinearity and The Ramsey RESET test to check for model misspecification. The probability value of the regression estimates was used to test the hypotheses of the study at 5% level of significance.

3.4 Model specification

To analyse the respective relationships defined in prior sections to achieve the proposed objectives, a panel regression model that utilizes fixed and random effect regression analysis was carried out based on the models formulated below in equation 1. Equation (i) and (ii) shows the implicit and the explicit form of the panel regression model. They are shown below:

$$ERP = f(\text{FSZ, PRO, LEV, AGE}) \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

The multiple regressions model with an error term (μ_t) is express in Eqn

$$ERP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{SIZE} + \beta_2 \text{PRO} + \beta_3 \text{LEV} + \beta_4 \text{AGE} + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Where: β_0 = Constant.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = coefficients of the explanatory variables

μ_t = error term over cross section and time.

A priori expectation

$$\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0, \beta_3 < 0, \beta_4 > 0$$

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

The various descriptive statistics that are discussed are minimum, maximum. Mean and standard deviation for all variables of the study to test for data normality. These are contained in Table 1.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics.

	ERP	SIZE	PRO	LEV	AGE
Mean	0.490072	0.475373	0.094810	2.091281	51.57292
Median	0.545455	0.470190	0.029493	1.942527	38.00000
Maximum	0.864346	1.238736	1.510478	7.613678	116.0000
Minimum	0.181818	0.100423	-0.557564	-2.149930	7.000000
Std. Dev.	0.180161	0.270939	0.264951	1.950893	33.95593
Skewness	0.114998	0.425586	2.550244	0.433373	0.628932
Kurtosis	1.722150	2.261869	12.89337	3.254444	2.070348
Jarque-Bera	6.743191	5.077331	495.5750	3.263968	9.785893
Probability	0.034335	0.078972	0.164320	0.195541	0.070499
Observations	96	96	96	96	96

Source: E-View 10.0 Result Output, 2025

The study on the effect of firm characteristics and environmental reporting practices of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria analyzed several variables including Environmental Reporting Practices (ERP), Size, Profitability, Leverage and Age. The mean ERP was 0.490072, with a median of 0.545455, a maximum of 0.864346, and a minimum of 0.181818. This reveals a moderate average level of environmental reporting practices. The standard deviation of 0.180161 indicates relatively low variability in ERP among the companies, while the positive skewness of 0.114998 suggests a slight skew to the right in the distribution of ERP values. The mean size of 0.475373 and median of 0.470190 indicate a relatively consistent company size within the sample, with a maximum of 1.238736 and a minimum of 0.100423. The standard deviation of 0.270939 highlights moderate variability in the size of the companies. The positive skewness of 0.425586 demonstrates a skew to the right, indicating that a few companies have significantly larger sizes compared to the majority.

The probability of the JarqueBera statistics measures the normality or otherwise of a time series data and assesses the model biasness for the variables of the study. The probability of the Jarque–Bera test values greater than 0.05 critical level ($p > 0.05$) implies that the datasets can be used for modeling an empirically meaningful relationship. This can further be illustrated in the histogram for all the variables of the study. The study suggests that the environmental reporting practices of the listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria are, on average, moderately high. The relatively low variability in ERP and size among the companies implies a certain level of uniformity within the industry. The skewness and kurtosis values for ERP and size indicate the distribution and shape of the data, shedding light on the patterns within the industry. These findings provide clue for policymakers, investors, and the companies themselves, helping them understand the current landscape of environmental reporting practices and firm characteristics within the Nigerian oil and gas sector.

4.1.3 Diagnostic Test

Test for Auto-Correction

Table 4: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

F-statistic	8.515103	Prob. F(2,89)	0.2004
Obs*R-squared	15.41919	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.2004

Source: E-views 10.0 Result Output, 2025

The Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test was performed to examine autocorrelation in the residuals of the study on the effect of firm characteristics and environmental reporting practices of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The F-statistic was found to be 8.515103, with a corresponding probability of 0.2004. Additionally, the Obs*R-squared value was 15.41919, with a probability of Chi-Square(2) also at 0.2004. These results indicate that there is no significant autocorrelation present in the residuals.

The LM test results imply that the assumption of no autocorrelation in the residuals of the model is not violated, as the probability values exceed common significance levels such as 0.05. This suggests that the error terms in the model are not systematically related to one another. Therefore, the LM test results provide confidence in the independence of the residual errors and the reliability of the estimated regression coefficients in the study, enhancing the validity of the findings in the study.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 5: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	1.885705	Prob. F(4,91)	0.1197
Obs*R-squared	7.348184	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.1186
Scaled explained SS	2.133270	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.7113

Source: E-views 10.0 Result Output, 2025

The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test, which is a type of Heteroskedasticity Test, was performed to determine if there is heteroskedasticity in the residuals of the study. The test yielded an F-statistic of 1.885705, with a probability of F(4,91) equal to 0.1197. In addition, the Obs*R-squared value was 7.348184, and the probability of Chi-Square(4) was 0.1186. These values indicate that there is no substantial evidence of heteroskedasticity in the residuals of the model. The findings of the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test suggest that the assumption of homoskedasticity is valid, as the probability values above commonly used significance levels such as 0.05. This indicates that the variability of the error terms in the model remains consistent across all values of the independent variables. Hence, the accuracy of the calculated standard errors and the soundness of the inferential findings about the impact of company characteristics and environmental reporting methods of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria are maintained.

Multicollinearity test

Table 7: Variance Inflation Factors

Variable	Coefficient	Uncentered	Centered
	Variance	VIF	VIF
SIZE	0.005664	2.971112	1.209278
PRO	0.005017	1.156875	1.024329
LEV	9.36E-05	2.237382	1.036585
AGE	3.45E-07	2.854939	1.157259

Source: *E-views 10.0 Result Output, 2025*

The Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) test in Table 7 examines the presence of multicollinearity among the independent variables of the study. The table presents both uncentered and centered VIF values. The centered VIF values, which are more commonly used to assess multicollinearity, are as follows: SIZE (1.209278), PRO (1.024329), LEV (1.036585), and AGE (1.157259). All these values are well below the commonly used threshold of 10, indicating a low level of multicollinearity among the independent variables. This suggests that the variables do not exhibit strong linear relationships with one another, allowing for more reliable estimation of the coefficients in the regression analysis.

The uncentered VIF values, which are typically less relevant for diagnosing multicollinearity but are included for completeness, show somewhat higher values: SIZE (2.971112), PRO (1.156875), LEV (2.237382), and AGE (2.854939). Despite the slightly higher uncentered VIF values, the centered VIF values confirm that multicollinearity is not a concern in this study. The low multicollinearity implies that the independent variables can provide distinct and separate explanatory power in modeling the effect of firm characteristics on environmental reporting practices. As a result, the study can confidently interpret the estimated coefficients and their significance without concerns about inflated standard errors or unreliable parameter estimates due to multicollinearity.

Table 8: Ramsey RESET Test

	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	0.065386	90	0.9480
F-statistic	0.004275	(1, 90)	0.9480
Likelihood ratio	0.004560	1	0.9462

Source: *E-views 10.0 Result Output, 2025*

The Ramsey RESET Test results presented in Table 8 assess the model specification in the study. The test is used to detect potential misspecification in the regression model, such as omitted variables, incorrect functional form, or measurement errors. The key values are the t-statistic (0.065386), the F-statistic (0.004275), and the Likelihood ratio (0.004560). All these values have corresponding p-values well above the conventional significance level of 0.05: 0.9480 for both the t-statistic and F-statistic, and 0.9462 for the Likelihood ratio.

These high p-values indicate that the null hypothesis of no misspecification cannot be rejected. In other words, there is no statistical evidence of model misspecification, suggesting that the chosen model adequately captures the relationship between the independent variables (firm characteristics) and the dependent variable (environmental reporting practices). The implications for the study are significant, as this result supports the validity of the model used, implying that the findings and inferences drawn about the relationship between firm characteristics and environmental reporting practices are reliable and not influenced by potential misspecification issues. This enhances the credibility and robustness of the study's conclusions.

4.1.5 Hausman Tests for Randomization of Panel Result

Hausman Tests for randomization of panel result test was performed to ascertain whether fixed effect or random effect regression results should be used for interpretation of results.

Table 9: Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	1.427832	4	0.8393

Source: *E-views 10.0 Result Output, 2025*

The Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test was employed to assess the suitability of the random effects model in the study. The test results indicate a Chi-Sq. Statistic of 1.427832 with 4 degrees of freedom, yielding a probability of 0.8393. This suggests that there is no significant difference between the random effects and fixed effects models, thus favouring the use of the random effects model. The implications of these results are important as they validate the selection of the random effects model over the fixed effects model for the study, ensuring that the model accurately captures the effect of firm characteristics and environmental reporting practices while accounting for the unique characteristics of each company in the sample.

4.1.6 Result of Regression Analysis

The relationship between the variables of the study was modeled through random effect regression analysis. Each coefficient represents the expected change in the dependent variable (environmental reporting practices) for a one-unit change in the corresponding independent variable, holding other variables constant. The regression result for the study is presented in thus:

Table 10: Fixed Effect Regression Result Coefficient

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
SIZE	0.241767	0.083390	2.899245	0.0054
PRO	0.102495	0.022287	4.590641	0.0002
LEV	-0.006899	0.009966	-0.692302	0.4905
AGE	0.000919	0.000605	1.519582	0.1321
C	0.449921	0.045888	9.804667	0.0000

Source: *E-views 10.0 Result Output, 2025*

Firm Size (SIZE)

The coefficient for SIZE is 0.241767, with a standard error of 0.083390 and a t-statistic of 2.899245, significant at the 0.0054 probability level. This positive and statistically significant coefficient suggests that larger firms are more likely to engage in environmental reporting practices. The implication is that as the size of the firm increases, so does the likelihood and extent of environmental reporting, possibly due to greater resources, stakeholder pressure, or regulatory scrutiny.

Profitability (PRO)

Profitability is a significant predictor of environmental disclosure (coefficient = 0.1025, standard error = 0.0223, $t = 4.59$, $p < 0.001$). This positive association suggests that more profitable firms are substantially more likely to engage in environmental reporting. Such firms

may possess the financial resources and strategic motivation to invest in environmental sustainability, potentially to bolster their public image and investor relations.

Leverage (LEV)

Leverage does not appear to significantly influence environmental disclosure (coefficient = -0.0069, standard error = 0.0100, $t = -0.69$, $p = 0.49$). While the negative coefficient hints at a potential inverse relationship between leverage and environmental reporting, this finding is inconclusive. Financial constraints or a focus on financial performance over non-financial metrics might explain this potential trend.

Firm Age (AGE)

Firm age does not significantly influence environmental reporting (coefficient = 0.0009, standard error = 0.0006, $t = 1.52$, $p = 0.13$). This coefficient is not statistically significant at the conventional levels, suggesting that the age of a firm does not significantly impact its environmental reporting practices. The positive but insignificant coefficient could imply that older firms might have more established reporting practices, but this relationship is not strong enough to be conclusive. The constant term (C) is 0.449921, with a standard error of 0.045888 and a highly significant t -statistic of 9.804667, indicating a p -value of 0.0000. This intercept represents the expected level of environmental reporting practices when all independent variables are zero. The significant and positive constant term indicates that even in the absence of the specific firm characteristics measured, there is a baseline level of environmental reporting practices among the firms. The R-squared value of 0.630108 indicates that approximately 63.01% of the variability in environmental reporting practices among listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria is explained by the independent variables included in the model (firm size, profitability, leverage, and firm age). The adjusted R-squared, which accounts for the number of predictors in the model and adjusts for potential over fitting, is lower at 0.406261, suggesting that about 40.63% of the variance in environmental reporting is explained after adjusting for the number of predictors. The F-statistic of 6.852222 and its associated p -value of 0.004882 indicate that the model is statistically significant, meaning that the independent variables collectively have a significant impact on environmental reporting practices. These statistics imply that while the model explains a moderate proportion of the variation in environmental reporting, there are other factors not captured by the model that could also influence these practices. The significant F-statistic confirms that the included variables are jointly important in explaining the dependent variable.

The results suggest that firm size and profitability are significant determinants of environmental reporting practices among listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. These findings indicate that larger and more profitable firms have both the capacity and the motivation to engage in such reporting. In contrast, leverage and firm age do not show significant effects, implying that financial structure and the firm's age do not play major roles in influencing environmental reporting practices. These insights can inform policymakers, regulators, and company managers about the factors that encourage environmental transparency and the areas where further improvements or support may be necessary.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Firms' size has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

Using the probability value of the estimate in accepting or rejecting hypothesis, the p value of the estimate is lower than the critical value of 0.05 confidence level. Thus, we reject the null

hypothesis. That is, we accept that the estimate b_1 is statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. This implies firms' size has a significant effect on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

H02: Profitability has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed oil & gas companies in Nigeria.

Based on the probability value of the estimate, $p(b_2) <$ critical value of 0.05 confidence level. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis. That is, we accept that the estimate b_2 is statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. This implies that profitability has a significant effect on environmental reporting of listed oil & gas companies in Nigeria.

H03: Leverage has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

Judging from the probability value of the estimate (i.e. $p = 0.4905$), we accept the null hypothesis. That is, we accept that at 5 percent level of significance, leverage has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

H04: Firms' age has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

On the basis of the probability value of the estimate ($p = 0.1321$), we accept the null hypothesis. That is, we accept that the estimate b_4 is statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. This implies that firms' age has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of Result

Firm Size (SIZE)

The study's findings indicate that firm size significantly affects environmental reporting practices among listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Larger firms are more likely to engage in such reporting, suggesting that these companies, possibly due to greater resources, stakeholder pressure, or regulatory scrutiny, are more inclined to disclose environmental information. This result aligns with the notion that larger firms have more visibility and accountability, which drives them to be more transparent about their environmental impacts. The study's rejection of the null hypothesis confirms that firm size is a significant determinant of environmental reporting, as demonstrated by the significant p-value of the coefficient for firm size.

Comparatively, the findings resonate with some previous empirical studies while diverging from others. For instance, Handoyo and Angela (2021) found that firm size and leverage significantly influence environmental disclosure quality, supporting the notion that firm characteristics play a crucial role in environmental reporting. However, the current study contrasts with Nkwoji (2021), who found no significant relationship between environmental expenditure and net profit in Nigerian oil and gas companies. While Nkwoji focused on the financial outcomes of environmental expenditures, the current study emphasizes the influence of firm size on reporting practices, highlighting a different aspect of the relationship between firm characteristics and environmental transparency. Similarly, Salawu et al. (2021) found no

significant relationship between firm age and environmental disclosure, aligning with the current study's results where firm age did not significantly impact environmental reporting.

The novelty in the current study lies in its specific focus on the oil and gas sector in Nigeria, using firm size as a primary variable influencing environmental reporting practices. Unlike previous studies, which often included various industries or different aspects of firm characteristics, this research isolates the effect of firm size within a specific, environmentally sensitive industry. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of company size in determining the extent of environmental disclosures, a perspective that is particularly relevant in a sector known for significant environmental impacts. This focused analysis highlights the need for targeted regulations and corporate strategies to enhance environmental transparency in the industry.

Profitability (PRO)

The study reveals a significant positive relationship between profitability and environmental reporting among listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Firms with higher profitability are more likely to engage in environmental disclosures, suggesting that these companies have the financial resources and possibly the motivation to enhance their public image and investor relations through transparency. The results demonstrate that profitability is a critical determinant of environmental reporting, as more profitable firms are better positioned to invest in and report on environmental initiatives. This finding leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, affirming that profitability significantly influences environmental reporting practices.

When comparing these findings with existing empirical studies, there are both consistencies and differences. For instance, Emmanuel, Elvis, and Abiola (2019) found that non-financial indicators of environmental disclosure positively affect performance, while performance indicators of environmental accounting disclosure had no effect. This aligns with the current study's finding that profitability, a performance measure, significantly influences environmental reporting. Conversely, Nkwoji (2021) found no significant relationship between environmental expenditure and net profit among Nigerian oil and gas companies, highlighting a divergence in results. This difference may stem from the specific focus on profitability as a driver of environmental disclosure rather than environmental expenditure per se.

The novelty of the current study lies in its specific focus on the oil and gas sector in Nigeria, examining how profitability influences environmental reporting within this particular industry. While previous studies have often looked at broader categories or different sectors, this research narrows down to an industry known for its environmental impact, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the factors driving environmental disclosures. Moreover, the study's use of profitability as a key variable offers new insights into how financial performance can serve as an incentive for transparency in environmental practices, highlighting a critical area for policymakers and industry stakeholders aiming to promote sustainable practices. This focused approach adds depth to the literature by considering industry-specific dynamics and their implications for environmental transparency.

Leverage (LEV)

The study finds that leverage (LEV) does not have a statistically significant impact on the environmental reporting practices of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The negative coefficient, though not significant, suggests a potential trend where highly leveraged companies might be less inclined to disclose environmental information. This could be attributed to the financial constraints these companies face, leading them to prioritize financial disclosures over

non-financial ones like environmental reporting. As a result, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant relationship between leverage and environmental reporting at the 5% significance level.

Comparing these findings with existing empirical studies, there are both similarities and contrasts. For example, Handoyo and Angela (2021) found that leverage significantly influenced environmental disclosure quality in Indonesian firms, highlighting a divergence in findings across different geographical and sectoral contexts. On the other hand, studies by Nkwoji (2021) and Polycarp (2019) in Nigeria also found no significant relationship between environmental expenditure (a related measure) and financial performance, aligning with the current study's result that leverage does not significantly affect environmental reporting. These studies collectively suggest that the financial structure, particularly leverage, may not play a crucial role in determining environmental disclosure practices in various contexts.

The novelty of the current study lies in its specific examination of the oil and gas sector in Nigeria, focusing on leverage as a factor influencing environmental reporting. While previous research has explored the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance broadly, this study narrows the scope to a particular financial metric (leverage) and industry, providing a more targeted understanding of the dynamics at play. This focus on leverage offers new insights into the potential financial pressures that might deter companies from engaging in environmental disclosures, an area less explored in the existing literature. This specificity helps in understanding the unique challenges faced by highly leveraged firms in disclosing environmental practices, contributing valuable knowledge to both academic research and industry practice.

Firm Age (AGE)

The study's findings indicate that the age of a firm (AGE) does not have a statistically significant effect on its environmental reporting practices among listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The positive but insignificant coefficient suggests that while older firms might have more established processes and experience in reporting, this factor alone is not a decisive influence on the extent or quality of their environmental disclosures. Consequently, the study accepts the null hypothesis, which posits that firm age does not significantly impact environmental reporting at the 5% level of significance.

Comparing these findings with existing empirical studies, there are both similarities and divergences. For instance, Salawu et al. (2021) also found that firm age does not significantly influence environmental disclosure among Nigerian oil and gas firms, aligning with the current study's results. Similarly, Uniamikogbo and Ifeanyichukwu (2021) observed no significant effect of firm age on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria, suggesting a broader trend where firm age may not be a critical determinant of environmental or financial outcomes. However, other studies like those by Majeed, Aziz, and Sale (2015) and Ahmed, Zakaree&Kolawole (2016) found that various firm characteristics, including board size and composition, significantly impact environmental disclosure, highlighting that factors other than firm age may be more influential.

The current study's focus on the oil and gas sector provides a specific context where the relationship between firm age and environmental reporting practices can be explored. This contrasts with broader studies that examine diverse industries or focus on different firm characteristics. The lack of significant findings related to firm age might suggest that in the oil and gas sector, regulatory pressures, industry standards, and other factors like board composition or financial performance play more critical roles in determining the extent and

quality of environmental reporting. This highlights the importance of considering sector-specific dynamics when analyzing the factors influencing environmental disclosures.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study was carried out to examine the effect of firm characteristics on environmental reporting practices of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. This section discusses the summary of the findings as well as the conclusions arising from the findings of the study. The part also presents suggestions for further empirical research to be conducted in this area of study.

5.1 Summary of Findings

After analyses of the data generated for this study from the selected oil and gas company in Nigeria, the following findings were made:

Size has a positive and significant ($p < 0.05$) effect on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

Profitability has a positive and significant ($p < 0.05$) effect on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

Leverage has a negative and insignificant ($p > 0.05$) effect on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

AGE has a positive but insignificant effect ($p < 0.05$) on environmental reporting of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

The study highlights the significance of firm characteristics in shaping the environmental reporting practices of oil and gas companies in Nigeria. It reveals that companies with greater resources and financial performance are more inclined to engage in environmental disclosure, highlighting the role of corporate size and profitability in promoting transparency and accountability. This trend suggests that such companies may prioritize sustainability and corporate responsibility, thereby enhancing their reputation and meeting the expectations of various stakeholders, including regulators, investors, and the public.

Moreover, the study suggests that other elements, such as regulatory frameworks and stakeholder pressures, play crucial roles in shaping environmental reporting practices. The intricate effect of leverage and the age of firms indicates that financial and historical factors alone are insufficient determinants of disclosure behaviour. This calls for a broader understanding of the dynamics at play, particularly in the context of emerging markets such as Nigeria. The findings emphasize the need for stronger regulations and incentives to encourage more comprehensive environmental reporting, ensuring that all companies, regardless of size or financial standing, adhere to transparent and responsible environmental practices.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations are considered appropriate based on the literature reviewed. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed for each variable:

- i. Large oil and gas companies should set industry standards for environmental reporting, while regulatory bodies should differentiate reporting requirements based on company size.

- ii. Government and stakeholders should encourage profitable companies to invest in environmental reporting by linking good practices with financial incentives like tax benefits or recognition awards.
- iii. Firms with high leverage should be provided with support mechanisms, such as financial incentives or grants, to encourage them to engage in environmental reporting despite financial constraints. On the part of the firm, leveraged firms should engage with stakeholders, including investors and creditors, to emphasize the importance of environmental transparency and its role in mitigating financial and operational risks.
- iv. Regulatory bodies and industry associations should provide continuous support and resources to firms of all ages, encouraging them to evolve and improve their environmental reporting practices over time.

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